

Unveiling the structure, chemistry, and formation mechanism of an in-situ phosphazene flame retardant-derived interphase layer in LiFePO_4 cathode

Abstract

The safety risks posed by the liquid electrolytes of lithium-ion batteries have drawn large-scale concern recently due to the increased reports of fires in electric vehicles and portable devices fuelled by these electrolytes. Efforts to address the fire safety of electrolytes have predominantly focused on the incorporation of flame retardant additives which generally lead to poor electrochemical properties when used in large quantities. Conversely, low amounts (~5 vol%) of fluorinated phosphazene-based flame retardants have been reported to yield non-flammable electrolytes while improving the battery's electrochemical properties. Herein, an advanced fire testing method, cone calorimetry, is employed to analyze a model electrolyte (ethoxy (pentafluoro) cyclotriphosphazene (EPCP) based electrolyte), which revealed that the fluorinated phosphazene-based flame retardant electrolyte with up to 6vol% only exhibit ignition delay rather than the widely acknowledged non-flammable behavior. Besides, for the first time, by employing a Time-of-flight secondary-ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS) and transmission electron microscopy, we clarify the chemistry and structure of a flame retardant-derived CEI layer formed on the LFP cathode surface. The CEI layer is characterized by a phosphorus and nitrogen (PN) rich layer, which inhibits the formation of a thick parasitic LiF layer which improves the cell's electrochemical integrity.

Keywords: electrode-electrolyte interphase, fire safety, cone calorimetry, flame retarded electrolytes, fire retardants

1. Introduction

The development of fire-safe, reliable, and low-cost rechargeable Li-ion batteries to cater for the ever-growing demands of numerous emerging fields, such as electric vehicles, grid storage, and advanced robotics, has recently received considerable attention from researchers in academia and the industry[1–6]. This has motivated extensive investigation of flame retardant electrolytes, which impart fire safety to lithium-ion batteries compared to the standard electrolytes, which readily burn on exposure to heat and a sufficient amount oxygen[7–9]. The main strategies employed to achieve this objective above include the use of intrinsic flame retardant electrolytes[10–12], ionic liquids[13,14], and the introduction of flame retardant additives into the electrolytes[15–19]. Among the aforementioned strategies, the introduction of flame retardant additives into the electrolytes holds great prospect from an industrial perspective due to the maintenance of current production lines[20]. Unfortunately, when used in large quantities, flame retardant additives often lead to poor electrochemical performance due to the negative impact on transport properties of the electrolytes and parasitic electrochemical reactions that occur at the electrode-electrolyte interface[16,21,22]. Hence, the development of new electrolytes that can simultaneously improve both fire resistance and electrochemical integrity of the batteries is crucial and urgent. Phosphorus and fluorine-rich compounds, can impart fire resistance and have attracted increased interest over the years[23–30]. Nevertheless, various drawbacks, such as rapid capacity fade, poor cycling performance, low rate capability, and low coulombic efficiency (CE), remain obstacles towards the practical application of the majority phosphorus-containing compounds[31–33]. The electrochemical unstable nature of the additives, negative effect on ion transport, destructive co-intercalation, depletion of electrolytes, and parasitic reactions with the electrolyte during cycling are widely considered as the primary sources of these drawbacks[34–37].

Recently, the introduction of fluorinated phosphazene-based flame retardant additives into flammable carbonate electrolytes has been reported in LIBs to simultaneously improve fire safety, cycling performance, rate capability, and coulombic efficiency [18,38–45]. A considerable number of works reported that a low amount (~5%, by weight/volume) of this additive can render the standard carbonate electrolytes non-flammable due to the ability of the flame retardant additive to act in the gas phase by releasing fluorine and phosphorus radical which bind to $O\cdot$ and $OH\cdot$ radicals that are released during combustion reactions[40,42,46]. This is not surprising since the commonly used fire testing methods, such as the direct burning test of the electrolyte using lighters, cannot provide sufficient heat flux to the electrolyte under study and hence may lead to unreliable conclusions. Besides, the battery cells fabricated with fluorinated phosphazene-containing electrolytes have also been shown to exhibit lower interfacial

resistance compared to the cells based on standard carbonate electrolytes, which is beneficial to the electrochemical performance[46,47].

Despite some modest success, the studies of electrolyte fire behavior, flame retardant mechanism, and the influence of flame retardant additives on the electrochemical properties remain challenging in the battery community. Although the high fire resistance of fluorinated phosphazene-containing electrolytes has been widely proven by researchers by employing rather simplistic approaches such as direct flame tests and self-extinguishing tests using common lighters[42,44]. No measurements have been reported using a reliable fire testing method to directly verify the improved safety of electrolytes of the fluorinated phosphazene-containing electrolytes. Thus, a measurement of the fire safety of the electrolytes using a more reliable method is necessary to clarify the real fire behavior of the fluorinated phosphazene-containing electrolytes. In addition, the investigation of the flame retardant mechanism will deepen our understanding of their mode of action to suppress fire in lithium-ion batteries.

Furthermore, there has been a limited understanding of the interphases generated on the surface of cathode materials in the reported cell compositions consisting of flame retardant electrolytes in general, owing partly to the complex influence of the flame retardant additives, which have not been recognized until recently[15,47,48]. Besides, the commonly employed surface-sensitive diagnostic equipment, such as X-ray and infrared spectroscopies to study the surface of electrodes, cannot spatially separate different components in electrodes. Undoubtedly, studies on the fire behavior of flame retarded electrolytes and flame retardant mechanism using advanced fire testing methods and evolved gas analysis, respectively, along with the studies on the influence of flame retardant additive on the composition of the CEI layer, are critical to the design and optimization of a new generation of batteries with simultaneously enhanced fire-safety and electrochemical integrity.

Herein, we employ cone calorimetry test (CCT) and thermogravimetry coupled to Fourier Transform Infrared (TG-FTIR) spectroscopy to clarify the real fire behavior of the fluorinated phosphazene-based electrolytes and fire suppression mechanism that takes place in the modified electrolyte respectively. Moreover, we employ time-of-flight secondary-ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS) for the first time to investigate the electrode-electrolyte interphases and the impact of the CEI layer on the overall cell performance in cells based on lithium iron phosphate cathode (LFP), with a particular focus on the role of the fluorinated Phosphazene based flame retardant additive. We clearly elucidate that the fluorinated phosphazene-based electrolyte with up to 6% of ethoxy (pentafluoro) cyclotriphosphazene (EPCP) exhibits a delayed ignition rather than a non-flammable behavior as it's widely acknowledged and propagated. On the other hand, we use the TG-FTIR technique to further investigate the fire suppression mechanism of the fluorinated Phosphazene based electrolyte. By employing techniques, such as time-of-

flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), we also observed a non-uniform and fragile CEI with rich carbonate solvent-derived species and thick LiF deposits formed on the surface of the electrode cycled in the standard carbonate electrolyte, which aids the surface deterioration of the cathode. In contrast, a flame retardant-derived CEI composed of rich phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N) species forms on the electrode surface cycled in the fluorinated Phosphazene based electrolyte, whose uniform and robust structure contribute to the prevention of corrosion on the surface of the cathode, hence leading to the enhanced cycling performance, rate capability and coulombic efficiency. This work not only provides a better insight into the fire behavior of fluorinated Phosphazene based electrolytes and their fire suppression mechanism but also sheds light on the role of fluorinated phosphazene additives in the generation of a uniform and robust CEI, which can inhibit the parasitic electrochemical reactions triggered by the HF attack.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Compositional analysis and Fire behavior of EPCP-based electrolytes

Figure 1. a Qualitative GC-MS chromatograms of 1M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC (LE), EPCP, 2 vol% EPCP in LE, 4vol% EPCP in LE and 6vol% EPCP in LE; b Mass Spectrum of LE and EPCP; c Key cone calorimeter test parameters histogram of LE containing different volume content of EPCP at 5 kw/m⁻²; d Key cone calorimeter test parameters histogram of LE containing different volume content of EPCP at

10 kW/m²; e Scheme of the cone calorimeter; f Illustration of an electrolyte sample burning during cone calorimetry test.

Electrolytes with various flame-retardant content were prepared by mixing different volume ratios of EPCP and the carbonate-based electrolyte (1M LiPF₆ in EC: EMC 1:1 by vol.). The contents of each sample are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Gas chromatography coupled to mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) was employed to characterize the composition of the prepared electrolytes (Figure 1a, b). Based on the mass spectra of the neat electrolyte and EPCP (Figure 1b), two main characteristic peaks at retention times 3.61 and 7.68 are assigned to the pristine electrolyte (LE, black line) and EPCP, respectively (red line). From the mass spectra, the main ion peaks at $m/z = 248$ and $m/z = 230$ are attributed to the EPCP molecule, in addition to that of the liquid electrolyte with ion peak at $m/z = 88$ attributed to the ethylene carbonate molecule in the electrolyte. Other physical properties of the solvents and flame retardant are also provided in Supplementary Table 2. Furthermore, the flame retardant was characterized using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. In the FTIR spectrum, EPCP exhibits its characteristic peaks at 2988 cm⁻¹ from C-H, 1260 cm⁻¹ from P-N. The peaks at 1066 cm⁻¹ and 953 cm⁻¹ are assigned to P=N and P-F, respectively, as shown in Figure S1 in the Supporting information. The NMR spectra of EPCP are shown in Figure S2 in the Supporting information. From the ¹H NMR spectrum, the following peaks were detected at 4.27–4.23 ppm (assigned to -CH₂-) and at 1.41–1.38 ppm (assigned to -CH₃), which are assigned to the saturated hydrogen of the ethyl groups. The ¹³C NMR spectrum exhibited peaks at 65.95 ppm and 15.46 ppm, which were also assigned to the ethyl groups. Moreover, the ³¹P NMR spectrum exhibited peaks at 15.27–15.02 ppm, 9.90 ppm, and 4.15–4.06 ppm, which are assigned to -PO-, -PF-, and -POF-, respectively. The EIS spectra of the LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes and digital photographs of the electrolytes with different content of EPCP are also shown in Figure S3a and b in the Supporting information, respectively. The impedance of the electrolyte slightly increases after the addition of 6 vol % of EPCP due to the increased viscosity of the electrolyte. This results in a slight decrease in the ionic conductivity of the electrolyte. (see Table 3, supplementary information).

Electrolyte fire resistance is a key property of the electrolyte that is required to ensure the overall safety of the battery[33,49]. The electrolytes were characterized using the cone calorimeter by applying two different heat fluxes of 5 kW m⁻² and 10 kW m⁻² based on a method previously reported by our group[50]. The corresponding key parameters, such as time to ignition, heat release rate, and total heat release of the electrolytes, are presented in Figure 1c, d, which shows the increased fire suppression behavior of electrolyte with increased content of the flame-retardant additive (see Video S1, S2, S3 and

S4 in the supporting information). Moreover, it is found that the ignition delay behavior exhibited by the flame LE-EPCP-based electrolytes is highly dependent on the heat flux supplied. However, due to the gas-phase mechanism of this flame retardant, increasing the content of EPCP in the electrolyte did not yield any significant reduction in the peak heat release rate (pHRR). Interestingly, the total heat released (THR, the integration of the area under the heat release curves) of the electrolyte samples exhibited a decline with the increased EPCP content in the electrolyte. These decreases in the THR values are attributed to the decreased burning time displayed by the EPCP containing electrolytes. Besides, while LE was totally burnt without any residue, the LE-EPCP based electrolytes left nearly 30% residue after burning (See Figure S4 in the supporting information). Table S4 in the supplementary information summarizes some key fire behavior parameters obtained from the cone calorimeter during the fire tests.

2.2 Fire suppression mechanism of the EPCP-containing electrolyte

As shown in the previous section, under the applied heat fluxes of 5 kW m^{-2} and 10 kW m^{-2} , the electrolyte samples exhibited a certain delayed ignition phenomenon, with the sample containing 6 vol% of EPCP exhibiting a time to ignition of 145s compared to the pristine electrolyte (LE) which was ignited after 10s. In order to investigate the mechanism of EPCP fire suppression, an evolved gas analysis of LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes was carried out by employing thermogravimetric analysis coupled to FTIR (TG-FTIR). The Gram-Schmidt curves of LE and LE-6EPCP are presented in the supporting information in Figure S5a. The intensities of the first peak exhibited by LE are higher than the first peak exhibited by LE-6EPCP, which thus indicates the release of a higher amount of volatile species by LE compared to LE-6EPCP. Moreover, a higher time resolution of the Gram-Schmidt curves (Figure S5b) revealed a clear contrast in the initial intensity, which further illustrated the location of a critical volatile intensity for ignition. Therefore, the fire-retardant action in the gas phase can be said to occur via volatile gas release rate retardation by the flame retardant. Figure S5e, f shows the FTIR spectra of the species detected in the first peak of the LE and LE-6EPCP, the detected FTIR spectrum of the species was found to closely match the spectrum of EMC.

2.3 Structural and Surface characterization of LFP

The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectrum of the LFP electrode is shown in Figure 2a. As expected, the full XPS spectrum shows the binding energy of Fe 2p, F 1s, P 2p, C 1s, and O 1s that were determined to be 710.4, 687.84, 133.16, 285.01, and 531.29 eV, respectively. However, a small N 1s peak is also detected in the spectrum at a binding energy of 400.09 eV, which is an impurity attributed to the purged nitrogen gas used by the manufacturer to seal the package of LFP electrode sheets under vacuum.

Moreover, with respect to lithium in the LFP, a peak is detected at a binding energy of 55.11 eV, which is the Primary XPS region of Li 1s. However, this peak is overlapped with Fe 3p doublet (Fe3p1/2 – Fe 3p3/2). In other words, there is an interference with the Fe 3p line to some extent. The Li 1s peak has very low sensitivity, therefore, is strongly affected by the Fe 3p peak because its relative sensitivity factor is about 30 times less than that of Fe 3p[51,52]. As there are no lithium secondary peaks (i.e lithium does not produce more XPS lines) to assist in confirmation, so it is difficult to quantify the lithium due to this interference.

Figure 2. a XPS Surface survey spectra of LFP electrode; b-c HRTEM images of LFP particles; d HAADF image of the sample; e-g EDS elemental mapping of LFP (P, O and Fe); h-i 2D Optical profilometry images of LFP electrode.

Furthermore, the TEM image of the LFP particles at different magnifications shows that the particles have a size of 200-300 nm (Figure 2b, c). HAADF images illustrate the morphology of the LFP particles

(Figure 2d). The distribution of the core elements Fe, P, and O was investigated using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) in scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM). Clearly, Fe, P, and O elements are homogeneously distributed throughout the LFP particles (Figure 2e-g), which promotes the stability of the electrode's structure. Moreover, as shown in Figure S13 in the supporting information, in-situ 1c patterns of LFP cycled with LE electrolyte clearly showed that the LiFePO₄ transforms to FePO₄ during the charging process with a clear shift in positions of the peaks to higher 2 θ and returns to its initial position during discharge, hence reverses to LiFePO₄. The optical profilometry (OP) technique was also employed to determine the surface topography of the LFP electrode. The OP analysis shows that the surface of the LFP cathode is quite rough with no apparent deposits on its surface.

2.4 Electrochemical performance investigations

Fluorinated phosphazene-based additives have been shown to improve key electrochemical performance in cells based on NMC[40,43] and LCO[44] cathodes, but to our knowledge, there are no reports of the performance of fluorinated Phosphazene containing electrolytes with LFP electrodes. Therefore, it is of great interest to investigate the performance of fluorinated phosphazene-containing electrolytes with LFP electrodes. In order to intuitively investigate the electrochemical performance of the LFP based electrodes, the LFP electrodes were cycled in LE (1 M LiPF₆/EC-EMC) and LE-6EPCP (6% EPCP + 94% 1 M LiPF₆/EC-EMC) of electrolyte at 100 mA g⁻¹ (0.6 C).

Figure 3. a. Cycling performance of LFP electrode in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes at 0.6 C (100 mA g^{-1}); b. rate capability of LFP cell cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes at different current densities; c. selected cycles specific of LFP cell cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes, respectively; d, e. selected cycles voltage profiles of LFP cell cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes, respectively; f. cyclic voltammogram (1st cycle) of LFP cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes; g, h, and i, j. 2D Optical profilometry images of LFP electrode cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes, respectively.

The coulombic efficiency (CE) of the LE electrolyte based cell remains around 98.5 percent before the 175th cycle, then briefly falls between 74.8 percent in the 176th cycle, then recovering to 97.8 percent in the 179th cycle and finally settling at 98.5 percent at the 200th cycle (**Figure 3a**), suggesting the occurrence of parasitic side reactions due to the relatively weak protection provided by cathode electrolyte interface[53]. In contrast, in the cell based on the LE-6EPCP electrolyte, the CE is maintained roughly at 99.8 percent, with no notable decline at the end of the 200th cycle. Notably, in comparison to the LFP cycled in the LE electrolyte which delivered a specific discharge capacity of 54 mAh g^{-1} (37% of its initial capacity) after 200 cycles, the LFP cycled in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte exhibited a superior cycling

performance with a specific discharge capacity of 98 mAh g^{-1} (70% of its initial capacity) over 200 cycles. The rate capability of the LFP electrode cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes at various current densities (25, 50, 100, 200, and 500 mA g^{-1}) was also studied. As illustrated in Figure 3b, the specific discharge capacity of LFP cycled in the LE electrolyte dramatically declines as the current rate increases. In contrast, at all the applied current densities, the LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte exhibited higher discharge capacities. This can be attributed to the easier diffusion of Li^+ through the LFP electrode cycled in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte[54]. The cycling performance of the LFP electrode in the LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes at 1C (170 mA g^{-1}) is also presented in supplementary Figure S6. Similarly, the LFP cycled in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte exhibited a superior cycling stability with a specific discharge capacity of 75 mAh g^{-1} (73.5% of its initial capacity) after 150 cycles. In contrast, the LFP cycled in the LE electrolyte exhibited a specific discharge capacity of 36 mAh g^{-1} (35% of its initial capacity) after 150 cycles. This indicates that even with the rapid intercalation and de-intercalation of lithium-ions at high current densities, the presence of EPCP in the electrolyte can contribute to stabilize the structure of the LFP electrode. It is worth noting that we also measured the impedance of the cells before cycling, and it was found that the cell based on LE-6EPCP electrolyte exhibited lower impedance before cycling compared to the cell based on the LE electrolyte (see supplementary Figure S7a). After cycling, the cell impedance was found to increase in the LFP cell based on LE electrolyte but comparatively lower in the LFP cell based on LE-6EPCP electrolyte as implied by the 200th cycle potential polarization. The polarization was larger by $\sim 80 \text{ mV}$ in LE (0.47V) compared to LE-6EPCP (0.39V) (see Supplementary Figure S7b). This further implies that the CEI formed on the LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte facilitates easier Li^+ ion diffusion compared to that formed on LFP electrode cycled in LE electrolyte [54,55]. Besides, as seen in voltage profiles (Figure 3d, e), the LFP electrode cycled in the LE electrolyte exhibited a higher potential polarization in the selected cycles, which is noticeably decreased in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte.

Besides, voltammetry studies (cyclic voltammetry and linear sweep voltammetry) were carried out to understand the role of EPCP in the observed electrochemical performance of LFP cells cycled with LE-6EPCP electrolyte. Interestingly, the CV curve (Figure 3f) of LFP in LE-6EPCP exhibited a new peak (3.3V) and a shift in de-intercalation peak of LFP from 3.10V to 3.15V. The appearance of a new peak and the peak shift indicate the formation of new species on the electrode surface. Moreover, another CV test at scan rate of 0.1 mV s^{-1} with a cut-off potential of 4.0-2.5 V was carried out for four cycles to verify if the detected peak persists in the subsequent cycles. As shown in Figure S14 in the supporting information, the peak was only detected in the first cycle, which is in agreement with the well-known first cycle

formation of the CEI layer. Further CV studies (Figure S15, supporting information) were also carried out at a scan rate of 0.1 mV s^{-1} cut-off potential of 4.0-2.5 V to view the intercalation/deintercalation peaks of lithium-ions in the LFP electrodes cycled with the LE and LE-6EPCP. In addition, the LSV result (Supplementary Figure S8) also exhibited a small increase current around 3.3V, which also indicates the formation of new species on the electrode surface. Furthermore, to investigate the mechanism and the role of the EPCP in alleviating the poor stability and low CE exhibited by the LFP cell cycled in LE, various post-mortem analytical methods were employed. The 2D and 3D optical images of the electrodes recovered from LFP cells cycled for 150 cycles at 1C (170 mA g^{-1}) in the LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes are shown in Figure 3g-j and Supplementary Figure S9a-d. It is seen clearly, that the electrode cycled in LE electrolyte shows more roughness, irregularities, and various deposits on its surface (Figure 3g, h) which are the result of the severe corrosion caused by HF attack on the outer surface of the electrode[55,56]. Nevertheless, and to our delight, this corrosion attack triggered by HF is remarkably inhibited in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte via the formation of a uniform passivation layer on the surface of the LFP electrode (Figure 3g, i). The measured surface parameters are summarized in Table 5 and 6 in the Supporting Information.

2.5 Influence of separator on cycling performance

Figure 4. a The cycling performance of LFP cell cycled at 0.6C in LE-6EPCP electrolyte with celgard 2400 and electrospun PVDF-HFP separators; b,c selected cycles voltage profiles of LFP cell cycled at 0.6C in LE-EPCP electrolyte with celgard 2400 and electrospun PVDF-HFP separators, respectively; d

heat release rate curves of celgard 2400 and electrospun PVDF-HFP separators; e TGA profiles of celgard 2400 and electrospun PVDF-HFP separators; f SEM image of electrospun PVDF-HFP separator.

Furthermore, the effect of separator choice on the cycling performance was investigated at 0.6C and 1C current rates in LFP cells based on the LE-6EPCP electrolyte (Figure 4a and Figure S10). Consequently, LFP cells were fabricated and compared with a commercial Celgard 2400 separator and electrospun PVDF-HFP separator. The results indicate that the LFP cells cycled with the electrospun PVDF-HFP based separator in LE-6EPCP electrolyte delivered superior cycling performance compared to electrode cycled with the Celgard 2400 separator in LE-6EPCP electrolyte. Essentially, at 0.6C current rate, the cell based on PVDF-HFP delivered superior cycling stability with a specific discharge capacity of 86 mAh g⁻¹ (84% of its initial capacity) after 100 cycles. In contrast, the cell based on Celgard 2400 exhibited a specific discharge capacity of 70 mAh g⁻¹ (68% of its initial capacity) after 100 cycles. Similarly, at a 1C current rate, PVDF-HFP delivered a superior cycling stability with 60% capacity retention, compared to Celgard 2400 which retained only 32% of its initial after 100 cycles. This improved performance is attributed to the better compatibility of the PVDF-HFP with the LE-6EPCP electrolyte as well as increased electrolyte uptake by the PVDF-HFP separator which is enabled by its highly porous fiber network. (Figure 4f and Supplementary Figure S11). Furthermore, the micro-combustion calorimetry test was employed to determine the fire behavior of the separators, the peak heat release rate (pHRR) of the PVDF-HFP separator was 71% lower than that of Celgard 2400, which indicates improved fire safety when PVDF-HFP separator is employed in the cell. In addition, the TGA result also indicated that PVDF-HFP produces more char residue during pyrolysis which further ascertains the improved fire safety.

2.6 Formation of flame-retardant derived CEI layer

The observed improvement of cyclic performance and rate capability of the LE-6EPCP based electrolyte compared to the pristine electrolyte (LE) can be explained by the clear contrast of the CEI layers formed on the surface of the LFP electrodes cycled in two different electrolytes. As seen in Figure 5a, a quite non-homogenous and irregular CEI layer is distinctly visible on the LFP electrode cycled in the pristine carbonate electrolyte (LE). Besides, the CEI layer's thickness is quite irregular. The thickest portion of the CEI was found to have a thickness of 9.2 nm while the thin portion of the CEI is about 1.3 nm, which increases the cell impedance as well as the surface degradation of cathode[57]. On the other hand, a sturdy, thin, and quite homogeneous CEI layer was formed on the surface of the LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte (Figure 5b), which was characterized by a relatively uniform thickness (around 2.6 nm), which facilitates the easy diffusion of Li⁺ ions while also reducing both the cell impedance and

the electrode corrosion[58]. Besides, the formation of a flame retardant-derived CEI is clearly evident from the voltammetry studies, essentially, an additional reduction peak appeared in the first cycle voltammogram of the LFP cycled with LE-6EPCP electrolyte around a voltage of 3.3V vs. Li^+/Li which was absent in the first cycle voltammogram of the LFP cycled with LE electrolyte (Figure 3f). Thus, the appearance of the peak during the reduction process indicates that the CEI formation on the LFP electrode cycled with LE-6EPCP also consists of a chemical species crosstalk mechanism from the lithium metal electrode to LFP electrode[59–61]. Moreover, as confirmed by the XPS surface survey spectra of the electrodes cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes after 150 cycles at 1C. The LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP showed higher peak intensities for N 1s and P 2p (Figure 5d) which strongly indicates that the outmost surface layer of the electrode consists of rich N and P species from the phosphazene structure in EPCP flame retardant additive. In contrast, very low amounts of N and P were detected on the LFP electrode's surface which was cycled in the LE electrolyte owing to the absence of the EPCP additive in the chemistry of the generated CEI layer. Figure 5e-l shows a more extensive analysis of the CEI layers generated on the LFP surface in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes. C–C/C–H, C–OH/C–O–C, and C=O detected in the XPS spectra of C 1s (Figure 5e) are believed to indicate the amount of the organic species in the CEI layer that are derived from the carbonate solvents[62]. As seen in Supplementary Table 7, the relative percentage of the C–C/C–H detected on the surface of the LFP electrode cycled in the LE electrolyte is 69.90 % compared to 61.95% for the electrode cycled in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte, indicating more organic species from the carbonate solvent constituted the CEI layer of the LFP electrode cycled in LE electrolyte. Moreover, the relative percentage of C–F (PVDF) in the LFP electrode cycled with LE is 0% compared to 14.12% in the electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP, which indicates the decreased degradation of PVDF (towards LiF formation) in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte[63]. The XPS spectrum of F 1s exhibits the content of fluorine from metal fluorides such as LiF and the PVDF binder in the CEI layer (Figure 5g, k). LiF is generally derived from the decomposition of the LiPF_6 salt[56] as well as the degradation of the PVDF binder[63]. While moderate amounts of LiF have been reported to be beneficial for battery performance, thick deposits of LiF are detrimental to the battery's electrochemical performance[42,64].

Figure 5. a, b. Post-cycling HRTEM images of LFP electrodes cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes, respectively; c, d. Post-cycling XPS surface survey spectra of LFP electrodes cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes, respectively; e–h. P 2*p*, N 1*s*, F 1*s* and O 2*p* high-resolution spectra of the LFP electrode cycled in LE electrolyte; i–l. P 2*p*, N 1*s*, F 1*s* and O 2*p* high-resolution spectra of the LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte.

Moreover, HF attacks on the electrode's surface are widely known to cause corrosion generating a large amount of LiF[65,66]. Apparently, a small quantity of LiF was detected in the CEI layer of the LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP (Figure 5k), as evidenced by the fluorine relative percentages of 19.67% and 80.33% from LiF and PVDF binder respectively. In contrast, a significantly larger amount of LiF (nearly 4 times the amount detected in LE-6EPCP) was identified on the surface of the LFP electrode cycled in LE electrolyte, with fluorine relative percentages of 77.28% and 22.72% from LiF and PVDF binder respectively (See Supplementary Table 8). In addition, the comparison of atomic ratios of P and N on the surface of the recovered LFP electrodes showed that a P and N species-rich CEI is preferentially generated on the LFP electrode cycled in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte (Supplementary Table 9). All the above results strongly suggest that the species from the phosphazene compound in the EPCP flame retardant additive preferentially participate in the CEI formation in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte, which is quite distinct from the pristine electrolyte (LE), in which species derived from the carbonate solvent

predominantly constitute the generated CEI layer. Therefore, the CEI layer of the LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP is rich in P and N species, which efficiently passivates the electrode surface, preventing HF corrosion as well as minimizing the formation of thick LiF deposits. As seen in Supplementary Table 9, the atomic ratio quantification results show that the nitrogen content on the LFP surface cycled in LE-6EPCP is 3.1 times more than that of the uncycled electrode. In contrast, the nitrogen content on the LFP surface of cycled in LE electrolyte did not significantly change compared to the uncycled electrode. All these results manifest that a flame retardant derived CEI (with rich P and N species) formed in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte, which is apparently beneficial to the LFP cathode via the inhibition of its rapid degradation.

Moreover, the TOF-SIMS technique was employed due to its high surface sensitivity, to characterize more accurately the chemistry of the generated CEI layers on the LFP cycled in the LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes. Various secondary-ion fragments (such as CH_3O^- , PO_2^- , PO_3^- , C_2^- , LiF_2^- , NO_3^- , and PNO^-) were detected, which are presented as a function of sputtering time. The NO_3^- , and PNO^- fragments represented species originating from the Phosphazene structure in the EPCP flame retardant additive and were detected only on the surface of the LFP cycled in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte. The CH_3O^- , C_2^- , are fragments are attributed to the organic species from carbonate solvent and the PVDF binder[67,68], while PO_2^- and PO_3^- fragments represent phosphate groups of LFP electrode[68]. The LiF_2^- , PO_2^- , PO_3^- fragments are constituting the inorganic species of CEI[67,69], The normalized TOF-SIMS depth profiles of the fragments detected on the respective CEI layers are presented in Figure 6a, b. The depth profiles of the fragments detected on the LFP electrodes cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP show that PO_2^- and PO_3^- fragments exhibited a relatively high normalized intensity and were detected earlier than other fragments except for C_2^- fragment which showed the highest intensity in the LFP electrode cycled in LE electrolyte. The high intensity exhibited by C_2^- fragment in LE electrolyte, demonstrates that the CEI layer of LFP in LE electrolyte originates predominantly from the carbonate solvent. Notably, in the LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP (Figure 6c), the PNO^- and NO_3^- fragments appear earlier than LiF_2^- fragment while also exhibiting high intensities compared to LiF_2^- , which indicate that the outer layer is composed mainly of species derived from phosphazene molecules in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte. On the contrary, in the LFP electrode cycled in LE, the signals of PNO^- and NO_3^- were not detected (see supporting information Figure S12).

Figure 6. a, b. TOF-SIMS normalized depth profiles of various secondary ion fragments detected on the surface of the LFP electrodes cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes, respectively; c. magnified depth profile some key secondary ion fragments of interest detected on the surface of LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte; d, e. TOF-SIMS chemical maps of various secondary ion fragments obtained over a sputtering time of 300 s on the LFP electrodes cycled in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes, respectively

Moreover, in the electrode cycled with LE electrolyte, LiF_2^- appeared earlier while also exhibiting a higher intensity compared to the electrode cycled with LE-6EPCP electrolyte, indicating the outer layer is made up of LiF_2^- species. The TOF-SIMS maps further provide visual evidence of the detected fragments and are presented in Figure 6d, e. In Figure 6e the maps show the presence of P and N rich species (PNO^- and NO_3^-) originating from the EPCP flame retardant in the outer layer of the LFP electrode cycled in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte compared with rich C and F species (C_2^- and LiF_2^-) in the outer layer of the LFP electrode cycled in the LE electrolyte (Figure 6d). Besides, the number of organic species CH_3O^- , C_2^- identified on the surface of LFP electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte show clear

distinction with those detected on the surface of the LFP electrode cycled in LE electrolyte. Accordingly, the depth profiles of the carbon-based fragments also reveal that the intensity of these organic species identified on the electrode surface cycled in LE electrolyte are relatively higher than those detected on the surface of the electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte (Figure 6a, b). These findings are in close agreement with the results obtained from the high resolution XPS analysis. Furthermore, the relatively higher intensity of LiF_2^- fragment on the electrode surface cycled in LE electrolyte is apparently indicative of a large amount of deposited LiF on the LFP surface. On the other hand, very little quantity of LiF_2^- was identified on the surface of the electrode cycled in LE-6EPCP electrolyte. All of these findings provide substantial evidence for the inhibition of both HF corrosion attack as well as the formation thick layers of LiF in fluorinated Phosphazene based electrolytes.

Figure 7. a. Schematic reconstruction of the CEI layer and fragment mosaics generated on the LFP electrode surface in LE electrolyte; b. schematic reconstruction of the CEI layer and fragment mosaics generated on the LFP electrode surface in LE-6EPCP electrolyte. The size of regions is not drawn to scale.

Figure 7a, b shows a schematic illustration of the CEI layers generated on the LFP electrodes in LE and LE-6EPCP electrolytes respectively. The diagrams were reconstructed based on the depth profiles obtained from the TOF-SIMS analysis of the CEI layer. As shown in Figure 7a, in the pristine electrolyte (LE), a non-uniform and inhomogeneous CEI layer formed on the LFP electrode, which could not protect the LFP cathode from HF attack, which led to the formation of thick LiF deposits on the LFP electrode. Hence, resulting in the generation of a thick CEI layer on the LFP electrode surface, which contributed to the increase in cell impedance [70,71], and the deterioration of cycling performance, low CE, and poor rate capability. On the other hand, the unique flame retardant fluorinated Phosphazene based electrolyte resulted in the preferential reduction of the EPCP additive in the first cycle, which products migrate via chemical crosstalk to form a robust and uniform CEI layer [59,72], that effectively protected the LFP electrode from attack by HF, leading to less LiF deposition on the surface.

3. Conclusion

This study revealed that fluorinated phosphazene-based electrolytes with content up to 6% (by vol.) cannot be deemed non-flammable because they burn when exposed to a sufficient amount of heat flux. However, it was found that they exhibit a certain ignition delay behavior which is highly dependent on the heat flux supplied to the electrolyte sample as well as the content of the fluorinated phosphazene-based additive. The fire suppression mechanism investigations also revealed that the presence of fluorinated phosphazene flame retardant effectively slows down and suppresses the amount of flammable volatiles released by the electrolyte under heating conditions. Besides, the corrosion attack of HF seriously affects the performance of LiFePO_4 , whereas the addition of fluorinated phosphazenes such as EPCP has a significant effect on the chemistry and nature of the CEI layer formed on the surface. Essentially, the formation of a robust and uniform CEI layer rich in P and N species in the fluorinated phosphazene-containing electrolytes has been identified to be correlated with the enhancement of key performance metrics of the cell such as rate capability, cycling performance, and coulombic efficiency. These findings provide strong evidence to decipher the superior cycling performance observed in the LE-6EPCP electrolyte based cells. While our findings of the chemical composition of the CEI layer provide a deeper insight into the chemistry of the complex CEI layer, for different electrode and electrolyte chemistries specific studies still need to be carried out especially when different flame-retardant additives are employed.

In summary, we elucidate the role of fluorinated Phosphazene in the fire suppression of liquid electrolytes and the definite correlation between the fluorinated phosphazene additives and the electrochemical performance of LFP based cells. This work provides valuable insights into the fire suppression mechanism of fluorinated phosphazene-containing electrolytes, and their effective role in the inhibition

of corrosion attack through the formation of flame-retardant derived passivation layer on the surface of LFP electrode.

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